

Special Relativity and Built-In Wave Solution

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Special relativity may be derived strictly for a particle with rest mass, either through $x'/t'=v$ considerations or more directly through the Newtonian ideas of $KE=.5m_0v^2$ and $p=m_0v$. A key idea of special relativity seems to be the complementarity of two frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ with respect to each other. A person in one frame thinks he/she is at rest and the other frame moving and vice versa. It is this complementarity which allows one to write an equation linking $m_0, p=0$ in a rest frame with m_0, E and p in a moving frame. Because $KE=.5m_0v^2$, if one considers this as an addition to m_0 to create E , then this complementarity equation is quadratic in m_0, E and p . A mathematical way to interpret this is to consider (pd, E) (d =constant with units of speed) as a vector which transforms and to consider a complementarity equation to be one of constant modulus (using a 1, -1 metric). This leads to the equation: $EE = ppdd + m_0m_0 dddd$ ((1)) which in turn yields $E=pd$ for $m_0=0$. If one starts with the notion of rest mass, it is unusual to set it to 0, but there is the constant speed d in the picture and so perhaps the $m_0=0$ case applies to it as it is the same in all frames. $E=pd$ may be mapped to a wave equation d =frequency*wavelength ((2)). This leads to the idea of $d=x/t \rightarrow -Et+px = 0$. This appears to be an invariant suggesting that (pd, E) transforms as (x, dt) . At the same time, $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$ and $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ for the wave solution. One may show that the Lorentz transformation developed for E, p yields $x/t=x'/t'=c$.

At this point, a wave equation $E=pc$ only holds for the d object which in turn is linked with x and t transforming in space. It seems, however, that the same x, t must transform for a particle with rest mass, thus the Lorentz transformation holds for both. Now $-Et+px$ is an invariant for both a d particle and particle with rest mass, but it is only 0 for the d particle (photon) as the wave solution only applies to the d particle (photon). The Δt and Δx are linked with action-reaction of the electric and magnetic fields of the photon and at the same time allow for $\Delta x / \Delta t = d=c$. As noted, the original equation ((1)) based on complementarity gives rise to the wave for $m_0=0$ and this is linked with an actual self-wave due to the electric and magnetic fields associated with a photon. For a particle with rest mass, m_0, E and p are strictly functions of m_0, v and c and seem to have nothing to do with a wave.

The point we make, however, is that the wave equation ((2)) is a dynamic equation because it involves velocity c . This velocity happens to be linked to frequency and wavelength, but ultimately describes motion in $x-t$. Thus, by removing rest mass, m_0 , the kinetic type energy linked with \hbar/p and \hbar/E allows for the dynamic propagation of the object (i.e. photon in this case), while in the m_0 case, it does not and seems to only be a fluctuation linked with possible interactions. In other words, the wavelength and frequency associated with p and E are always present, but only clearly manifest themselves in the equation $E=pc$ for $m_0=0$, a situation in which they actually govern dynamic motion in space because m_0 is no longer present to regulate the speed, so to speak.

Lorentz Transformation from Newtonian Mechanics

We have argued in previous notes that Newtonian mechanics points to a Lorentz transformation, but only if one considers the complementarity of two frames which move at a relative constant speed to each other. The point seems to be that a person in one frame thinks he/she is at rest, while the other moves and vice versa. It is not the case that a particle at rest is the same as a moving one, but rather that there is a complementarity of the two frames, i.e their co-ordinate axes, we argue. It is this complementarity which allows one to write an equation linking m_0 (rest) to E, p, m_0 for motion. The result is based on $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ which seems to be an addition to m_0 as it has no direction. Then, one requires $p = m_0 v$, but now there is a m_0 factor and so one should use: $(m_0 + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2/c^2)$. This leads to:

$$(m_0 + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2/c^2) - (m_0 v)(m_0 v) \approx m_0 c^2 \quad ((3))$$

$$((3)) \text{ is the approximate result of: } E = pc + m_0 c^2 \text{ where } d=c \quad ((4))$$

Thus, Newtonian mechanics and complementarity yield the quadratic complementarity equation of special relativity. A more mathematical approach might be to introduce a matrix transformation such that $(0, m_0)$ transforms to (p, E) such that the modulus, using a $(1, -1)$ type metric yields $((4))$.

Given that p should be proportional to m_0 and v , one may write:

$$\begin{aligned} |g(v) &= g(v) v| \quad ((5)) \\ |vg(v) &= g(v)| \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Using } ((4)), \text{ one may then find that } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((6))$$

The results above have been derived for $m_0 > 0$, but there is nothing preventing one from setting $m_0 = 0$ in $((4))$ and interpreting E and p as energy and momentum of an object with no rest mass, such as a photon. In other words, one has:

$$E = pc \quad ((7)) \text{ For a photon, } d=c$$

$((7))$ is equivalent to a wave-equation: $\text{velocity} = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength}$.

A main point we wish to stress is that $((7))$ is a dynamical equation because velocity c measures the motion of the object in $x-t$. The frequency and wavelength are physical observables linked to this motion, but it is the motion which is stressed. Thus, for the particle with rest mass, the motion v is key and for the $m_0 = 0$ particle (photon), $c = d$ is key.

At this point, there is no notion of using the above transformation $((5))$ for x, t . It has only been applied to p, E . $((7))$, however, suggests that if one writes: $c = x/t$, that:

$$-Et+px = 0 \quad ((8))$$

((8)) now contains x and t in such a manner that (x, ct) should transform as (pc, E) because ((8)) is an invariant. In other words, the wave solution leads to the idea of the Lorentz transformation applying to a x - t as well as E - p .

This, we argue, leads to an interesting result. If one considers Newtonian mechanics for a rest mass, m_0 , then one may use ((5)) with $g(v)=1$. Then:

$$x=0, t \rightarrow x'=vt \text{ and } t'=t \quad ((9))$$

There is no $g(v)$. This result, however, cannot hold for a photon because it must have:

$c=x/t = x'/t'$ because c is a constant holding in all frames. If one uses ((5)) with $g(v)=1$ then:

$$x'/t' = (x+vt) / (vx+t) = (1+v)/(v+1) \text{ (here } c=1) \text{ This is not equal to } c \quad ((10))$$

Thus, there must be a $g(v)$ value.

For a photon, it is known that one has wave motion and so $-Et+px=0$ is linked with riding a rest with E and p linked to:

$$\Delta t = \text{constant}/E \text{ and } \Delta x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((11))$$

The key idea, however, is that this energy creates the dynamic speed c . A particle with rest mass has kinetic energy (Newtonian $KE = \frac{1}{2}m_0v^2$), but this does not govern the speed, it is linked with the inertial m_0 . That does not prevent ((11)) from applying to a particle with rest mass, we argue, it just means that the fluctuations (periodic) of ((11)) do not give rise to the speed. In other words, m_0 prevents one from having a self-wave as in the photon case, but does not prevent the fluctuations ((11)) from existing. It is only when one has the photon case, that one may see these fluctuations clearly in the equations because they govern the speed c . After all, the Newtonian mechanics linked with obtaining the Lorentz transformation are also about m_0 and v and not about any fluctuations. Thus, these fluctuations are not readily visible in equations because they do not govern motion in the m_0 case, but become visible when they are responsible for motion in the photon case.

We have suggested in previous notes that there is a hint of their presence in the m_0 case because for:

Constant = $-Et+px$ (where $x/t=v$) the fluctuations ((11)) do not change the constant value if they are added to t and x .

Constant = $-Et+px$ (the action) governs the dynamical motion, but the fluctuations ((11)) do not change this motion on average. They are still present, however, as 2-slit interference occurs for a particle with rest mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the idea of $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ only clearly emerges for the photon case because it is only in this case that these periodic fluctuations govern dynamical motion. In other words, Newtonian mechanics and even special relativity deal with v which is a dynamical value. The fluctuations are apparent when one has a wave-equation because m_0 has been removed. Thus, it seems that m_0 is directly linked to the dynamical motion v in the $m_0 > 0$ case, but that does not mean that E and p necessarily cease to fluctuate (periodically) as \hbar/E , \hbar/p . The wave equation only reveals them because m_0 is gone (0) and something needs to govern the motion, but also be linked with action-reaction as a photon interacts. E and p are linked with interaction and in the case of motion for $m_0 > 0$, it seems that this same periodicity/fluctuation may be present. We argue that this is hinted at by $\text{constant} = -Et + px$ for $m_0 > 0$. This action describes dynamical motion, i.e. $x/t = v$, but $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, added to t and x in this equation do not change the constant. Thus, one still has the same v dynamical motion, but one may also have the fluctuations, as in free particle quantum mechanics.